

COMPARATIVE TYPOLOGY OF ADJECTIVES IN ENGLISH-UZBEK LANGUAGES AND TRANSLATION PROBLEMS

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Annotation: this article is devoted to the discussion of comparative typological aspects of adjectives in English and Uzbek languages.

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INTRODUCTION

Morphology is the general category that can be typologically compared in both English and Uzbek languages. In the morphological process occur to English adjective, there are some classes of word which can be modified by either derivational or inflectional affixes to form the grammatical category of adjective. There are two types of adjectives in English: single-syllable and multi-syllable. For example: small car - a single-link quality; important subject - a multi-link quality. As mentioned above, there are three levels of quality: simple, comparative, and incremental.

MAIN PART

LEVEL OF ONE-LINKED QUALITIES

1. At the simple level of one-syllable adjectives, no addition is added to the adjective, and the adjective itself is written. For example: Small car – kichik mashina. Big garden – katta bog`. Strong man – kuchli odam.

2. At the comparative level of one-syllable adjectives, the suffix "-er" is added to the adjective. This suffix corresponds to the Uzbek suffix "-roq". For example: Smaller car – kichikroq mashina. Bigger garden – kattaroq bog`. Stronger man – kuchliroq odam.

3. To make the accrual level of one-syllable adjectives, the suffix "-est" is added to the adjective, and the definite article "the" is always placed before the adjective at the accusative level. The suffix "-est" in English corresponds to the word "eng" in Uzbek. For example: The smallest car – eng kichik mashina. The biggest garden – eng katta bog`. The strongest man – eng kuchli odam.

Superlative does not tolerate any comparison. He stands above all and does not hide it, for he is the most, the most. Before embarking on the formation of new forms of proportion, it is necessary to ask, comparatively and perfectly, how many syllables a word has. Depending on the next answer, two methods of teaching are distinguished: If a word consists of one or two syllables, the exact

article is added to it and the ending -est: clean - the cleanest (clean - the cleanest), great - the biggest (great - the greatest), sharp - sharp (sharp - sharp). If a word consists of three or more syllables, an additional word will appear in front of it with the most or least definite article: thin - the thinnest (terrible - the thinnest), terrible - the most terrible (terrible - the most terrible), difficult - the most difficult (difficult - the most difficult). If adjectives consisting of one or two syllables end with a dumb vowel sound, it falls when you add the vowel or -est numbers: cute - cute - cute (cute - cute - cute). If the short adjective ends with -y, this letter changes to -i with the addition of -er or -est: hungry - hungry - ochgriest (hungry - opener - hungry). When a short consonant ends with a vowel and a vowel consonant, when the vowel adds the number -er or -est, the last consonant is added: fat - fat - fat (thick - thick - thick) [1].

Morphology is the study of words, how they are formed, and their relationship to other words in the same language. It analyses the structure of words such as stems, root words, prefixes, and suffixes. In the twentieth century the term was extended to the branch of grammar that investigates the structure of words which investigates the sentence structure. Morphological typology is a way of classifying the languages of the world group languages on the basis of how those languages form by combining morphemes. The primary categories exist to distinguish all languages: analytic languages and synthetic languages, where each term refers to the opposite end of a continuous scale including all the world's languages.

In both English and Uzbek languages the adjective qualifies or modifies a substance:

English Uzbek

a **red** apple **qizil** olma

a **clever** student **aqli** talaba a **new** building **yangi** bino

red pepper **qizil** qalampir

In the languages compared the adjective has the grammatical category of the degrees of comparison and typical stem building morphemes:

English adjectives: **a-** (amoral), **ab-** (abnormal), **demi-** (demi season), **di-** (diatomic), **dia-** (diachronic), **extra-** (extraordinary), **il-/im-/in-/ir-**(illegal), immature, inadmissible, irrespective), **post-** (post-free), **pre-** (prechristian), **un-** (unpleasant), - **able/ible** (valuable, flexible), **-al**(natural), **-an/- ean /- ian** (American, Mediterranean, cyclopedian), **- ant** (disputant), **-ary** (revolutionary), **-ate** (elaborate) **-ed** (talented), **-en** (silken), **-esgue** (grotesgue), **-fold** (twofold), **-ful** (careful), **-ic** (syllabic), **-ish** (bluish), **-ive** (impulsive), **-less** (homeless), **-like**

(childlike), **-ly** (tigerly),- **most** (heedmost), **-tory / -ory** (explanatory, modulatory), **-ous** (furious), **-some**(lonesome), **-y** (shady), **-ical** (logical).
Uzbek adjectives: **ba-** (badavlat), **be-** (beg'am),**bo-** (boadab), **no-** (noaniq), **bad-** (badnafs),- **li**(kuchli), **-siz** (kuchsiz), **-gi, -ki, -qi** (tunggi, chillaki,tashqi), **-dagi** (ruldagi), **-chan, / -chang** (ishchan, ko'ylakchang), **-chil** (epchil), **iy-** (nazariy), **-simon** (odamsimon), **-ik, / -iq, / -uq** (egik, qiyshiq, quruq), **-ma** (ezma), **-qoq / - g'oq** (tarqoq, toyg'oq), **-choq, / -chiq** (erinchoq, qizg'anchiq), **-kir, / -qir** (o'tkir, chopqir), **-g'on** (bilag'on), **-iv** (intensiv), **-ik** (demokratik), **-al** (aktual) [4].

In English and Uzbek the adjective usually forms combinations with:

1. nouns:

Eng.: an *interesting* book, a *tall* tree, a *strong* man etc.

Uzb.: *qiziqarli* kitob, *baland* daraxt etc.

2. link-verbs:

Eng.: was *strong*, was *clever*, was *old*

Uzb.: *kuchli* edi, *aqlli* edi, *qari* edi

3. adverbs:

Eng.: very *interesting*, very *old*

Uzb.: juda *qiziqarli*, juda *eski*

In English the adjective can combine with the so-called prop word " **one**" (the **red one**, the **yellow one**). In the languages compared the typical functions of the adjective are those of attribute and predicate:

The adjective as an attribute:

Eng.: I have brought him an *interesting* book.

Uzb.: Men unga *qiziqarli* kitob olib keldim.

4. **The adjective as a predicative** Eng.: The book was **interesting**. Uzb.: Kitob **qiziqarli** edi.

According to their structure English and Uzbek adjectives may be:

1. simple:

Eng.: red, good, hot, cold, slow

Uzb: qizil, yaxshi, issiq, sovuq, sekin

2. derivative:

Eng.: passive, talented, social, snowy Uzb,: noaktiv, talantli, kirishimli,qorli

3. compound:

Eng.: big-eyed, deaf-mute, eagle-eyed,never-ending

Uzb.: xushbo'y, vatanparvar,
uchburchakli, odamsimon

On the base of their meaning adjectives are grouped into qualitative and relative classes. Qualitative adjectives express the property of nouns by means of special words denoting: *opinion, colour, size, shape or physical quality, taste, smell, age, origin, material, qualifier/purpose* etc [5].

CONCLUSION

Morphological unit plays an essential role to learn e.g. reading texts easily, gives vocabulary knowledge to identify words and recognize their meanings while they engage with the learning word or reading one. The adjective - a grammatical part of speech modifies and describes a noun. Furthermore, it tells some descriptive ideas of the noun and they are: size, color, shape, origin, state, character and etc. Because of the differences of geographic environment of the two nations, the grammatical structures of the part of speech – there are some differences in forming the words of adjectives, adding the prefixes and suffixes, forming of comparison degrees and etc. Some adjectives may have more one field, so it is difficult to define the made words from the root ones. The distinctive feature of Uzbek language word formation way is composition which can not be found in other compared languages. Finally, from the analysis of compared languages can be found several similarities, it is possible to show the existence of types of affixation in both languages, or amount of derived words or suffixes, which can change the meaning from one part of speech into another.

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